

Spectrophotometric determination of Buclizine as hydrochloride (BUCZ) using I₂/PMAP-SAc, AM/PTC and PMA/cobalt(II)/EDTA

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Abstract : Simple, accurate and reproducible UV spectrophotometric methods were established for the assay of BUCZ based on the formation of precipitation, charge transfer and redox products. Precipitation/charge transfer complex formation of the BUCZ with I₂/*p*-*N*-methyl amino phenol sulphate (PMAP)-sulphanilic acid (SAc) by Method A, the precipitation/complex formation with ammonium molybdate (AM)/potassium thiocyanate (PTC) by Method B and precipitation/redox reaction of BUCZ with phosphomolybdic acid (PMA)/Co^{II}/EDTA by Method C were proposed. Determination of BUCZ in bulk form and in pharmaceutical formulations were also incorporated.

Keywords : Estimation, Buclizine, precipitating agent, charge transfer complex.

Introduction

Buclizine (as hydrochloride, BUCZ) is a piperazine antihistamine with antimuscarinic and central sedative properties. It is mainly used for its antimetic action, particularly in the prevention of motion sickness when it should be given at least 30 min before traveling. It is also used in combination with analgesics to treat migraine attacks.

A very few physico-chemical methods appeared in the literature for the assay of BUCZ¹ in biological fluids and pharmaceutical formulations. Most of them are based on visible spectrophotometric methods^{2,3}, HPLC⁴⁻⁸, GC^{9,10}, fluorimetry¹¹⁻¹³, LC-MS¹⁴, GC-MS¹⁵⁻¹⁷ and TLC¹⁸, Mass¹⁹. The analytically useful functional groups in BUCZ have not been fully exploited for designing suitable visible spectrophotometric methods and so still offer a scope to develop few more visible spectrophotometric methods with better sensitivity, selectivity, precision and accuracy. The author has made some attempts in this direction and succeeded in developing visible spectrophotometric methods by exploiting various functional groups of BUCZ with I₂/PMAP-SAc, AM/PTC, PMA/Co^{II}-EDTA. All these methods have been extended to pharmaceutical formulations as well.

Experimental

An Elico, UV-Visible digital spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched quartz cells were used for the spectral and absorbance measurements. An Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used for pH measurements.

All the chemicals and reagents used were analytical grade and the aqueous solutions were freshly prepared with triple distilled water. A 1 mg/ml solution was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of pure BUCZ in 5 ml of 0.1 *N* HCl followed by dilution to 100 ml with distilled water and the stock solution was diluted stepwise with distilled water to get the working standard solutions of required concentrations. I₂ solution (E. Merck; 0.089%, 3.5 × 10⁻³ *M*), PMAP (*p*-*N*-methyl amino phenol sulphate) solution (Loba; 2%, 5.807 × 10⁻² *M*), SAc (sulphanilic acid) solution (Sd-fine; 0.4%, 2.309 × 10⁻² *M*), hydrochloric acid (E. Merck, 1 *M*) were prepared for Method A. AM (ammonium molybdate) solution (E. Merck; 2%, 1.618 × 10⁻² *M*), PTC (potassium thiocyanate) solution (Ranbaxy; 10%, 1.029 *M*), HCl concentrated (E. Merck) were prepared for Method B. PMA (phosphomolybdic acid) solution (Rea chem; 4%, 2.194 × 10⁻² *M*), cobalt nitrate solution (BDH; 3%, 1.03 × 10⁻¹ *M*), EDTA solution (Sd-fine; 4%, 1.07 × 10⁻¹ *M*), acetone (Qualigens) were prepared for Method C.

Recommended procedures :

Method A :

Aliquots of standard BUCZ solution (0.5–3.0 ml, 40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) were delivered into a series of centrifuge tubes. Then 2 ml of (1 M) HCl and 2 ml (3.5×10^{-3} M) of I_2 were added successively. The volume was made upto 7 ml with distilled water and kept aside for 15 min and centrifuged for 5 min. The precipitate was collected through filtration and subsequently washed with 2 ml of distilled water. The filtrate and washings were collected in a 25 ml graduated tube. Then 3.0 ml of PMAP (5.807×10^{-2} M) and 2.0 ml of SAc (2.309×10^{-2} M) solutions were added successively and the volume was made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance was measured after 25 min at 520 nm against distilled water. A blank experiment was also carried out omitting the drug. The decrease in absorbance and in turn the drug concentration was obtained by subtracting the absorbance of the test solution from the blank. The amount of BUCZ was calculated from Beer's law plot (Fig. 1).

Absorption spectrum of BUCZ- I_2 /PMAP-SAc

Fig. 1. Beer's law plot of BUCZ- I_2 /PMAP-SAc

Method B :

Aliquots of standard BUCZ solution (0.5–3.0 ml, 100

$\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) were delivered into a series of centrifuge tubes and the volume in each tube was adjusted to 3.0 ml with distilled water. Then 1 ml (1.618×10^{-2} M) of ammonium molybdate was added and centrifuged for 5 min. The precipitate was collected through filtration followed by washing with 50% alcohol until it is free from the reagent. The precipitate in each tube was dissolved in 5 ml of acetone and transferred into a 25 ml graduated tube. Then 5 ml of conc. HCl and 3 ml (1.029 M) of potassium thiocyanate were added successively. The tubes were kept aside for 20 min at laboratory temperature. The solution in each tube was made upto the mark with distilled water. The absorbance was measured at 470 nm against a similar reagent blank. The amount of BUCZ was calculated from Beer's law plot (Fig. 2).

Absorption spectrum of BUCZ-AM/KSCN

Fig. 2. Beer's law plot of BUCZ-AM/KSCN

Method C :

Aliquots of standard BUCZ solution (0.5–3.0 ml, 400 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) were delivered into a series of centrifuge tubes and the volume in each tube was adjusted to 5.0 ml with distilled water. 2 ml (2.194×10^{-2} M) of phosphomolybdic acid was added and centrifuged for 5 min. The precipi-

tate was collected through filtration followed by washing with distilled water until it is free from the reagent. The precipitate in each tube was dissolved in 5 ml of acetone and transferred into a 25 ml graduated tube. 1 ml ($1.03 \times 10^{-1} M$) of cobalt nitrate and 1 ml ($1.07 \times 10^{-1} M$) of EDTA solutions were successively added and the tubes were heated for 12 min at 60 °C. The tubes were cooled and the solution in each tube was made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance was measured at 840 nm against a similar reagent blank. The amount of BUCZ was calculated from Beer's law plot.

Results and discussion

The optimum conditions for the color development of Methods A, B and C were established by varying the parameters one at a time, keeping the others fixed and observing the effect produced on the absorbance of the

colored species.

The optical characteristics such as Beer's law limits, molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity for the Methods (A-C) are given in Table 1. The precision of the method to the drug was found by measuring the absorbance of 6 separate samples containing known amounts of drug and the results obtained are incorporated in Table 2. Regression analysis using the method of least squares was made to evaluate the slope (b), intercept (a), correlation coefficient (r) and standard error of estimation (S_e) for each system.

The accuracy of the methods was ascertained by comparing the results of proposed and reference methods statistically by the t - and F -tests. The comparison shows that there is no significant difference between the results of studied methods and those of the reference ones. The similarity of the results is obvious evidence of the fact

Table 1. List of proposed and reported visible spectrophotometric methods

Type of reaction	Reagent	Method	Optical characteristics		
			λ_{\max} (nm)	ϵ_{\max} (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Beer's limits ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)
Precipitation/ charge transfer complex formation	I ₂ /PMAP-SAc	Method A	520	5.599×10^4	0.8–4.8
Precipitation/ complex formation	AM/PTC	Method B	470	2.544×10^4	2–12
Precipitation/ redox	PMA/Co ^{II} -EDTA	Method C	840	7.134×10^3	8–48

Table 2. Optical and regression characteristics, precision and accuracy of the proposed methods for BUCZ

Parameter	Method A	Method B	Method C
λ_{\max} (nm)	520	470	840
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.8–4.8	2.0–12.0	8–48
Detection limit ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.1602	0.3955	2.543
Molar absorptivity (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	5.599×10^4	2.544×10^4	7.134×10^3
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}/0.001$ absorbance unit)	4.290×10^{-2}	7.318×10^{-2}	0.1641
Optimum photometric range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	2–3.98	8.13–12	16–40
Regression equation ($Y = a + bc$) slope (b)	0.1131	0.05276	0.02429
Standard deviation on slope (S_b)	2.262×10^{-3}	9.940×10^{-4}	4.567×10^{-3}
Intercept (a)	7.5×10^{-4}	2.75×10^{-3}	9.999×10^{-3}
Standard deviation on intercept (S_a)	6.003×10^{-3}	6.593×10^{-3}	1.212×10^{-2}
Standard error on estimation (S_e)	5.723×10^{-3}	6.287×10^{-3}	1.155×10^{-2}
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9994	0.9995	0.9988
Relative standard deviation (%)	8618	0.7814	0.6763
0.05 level	0.9909	0.8985	0.7776
0.01	1.553	1.408	1.219
% error in bulk samples	-0.241	0.348	-0.298

that during the application of these methods, the excipients are usually present in pharmaceutical formulations do not interfere in the assay of proposed methods. As an additional check of accuracy of the proposed methods, recovery experiments were carried out. The recovery of the added amounts of standard drug were studied at 3 different levels. Each level was repeated for 6 times. From the amount of drug found, the % recovery was calculated in the usual way.

The higher λ_{\max} values of all the proposed methods have a decisive advantage since the interference from the associated ingredients should be generally less at higher wavelengths than at lower wavelengths. Thus the proposed visible spectrophotometric methods are simple and sensitive with reasonable precision, accuracy and constitute better alternatives to the existing ones to the routine determination of BUCZ in bulk forms and pharmaceutical formulations.

Method A

Step I :

Step II :

Method B

Step I :

Step II :

Method C

Step I :

Step II :

Table 3. Assay of BUCZ in pharmaceutical formulations

Formulations	Amount taken (mg)	Amount found by proposed methods			Reference method	Percentage recovery by proposed methods		
		Method A	Method B	Method C		Method A	Method B	Method C
Tablet I	25	24.83 ± 0.32 <i>F</i> = 2.54 <i>t</i> = 0.5	25.12 ± 0.33 <i>F</i> = 2.388 <i>t</i> = 0.7010	24.74 ± 0.42 <i>F</i> = 1.474 <i>t</i> = 0.7821	24.95 ± 0.51	99.77 ± 0.69	99.85 ± 0.84	99.47 ± 0.75
Tablet II	25	24.72 ± 0.49 <i>F</i> = 1.60 <i>t</i> = 1.6241	24.63 ± 0.53 <i>F</i> = 1.368 <i>t</i> = 0.8735	25.12 ± 0.37 <i>F</i> = 2.807 <i>t</i> = 0.6997	24.92 ± 0.62	99.73 ± 0.91	99.52 ± 0.61	99.43 ± 0.74
Tablet III	25	24.63 ± 0.26 <i>F</i> = 3.267 <i>t</i> = 2.325	24.85 ± 0.35 <i>F</i> = 1.803 <i>t</i> = 1.140	24.91 ± 0.42 <i>F</i> = 1.252 <i>t</i> = 0.8173	25.12 ± 0.47	99.81 ± 0.77	99.96 ± 0.98	99.67 ± 0.97
Tablet IV	25	24.51 ± 0.49 <i>F</i> = 2.800 <i>t</i> = 1.031	24.43 ± 0.73 <i>F</i> = 1.261 <i>t</i> = 1.050	25.12 ± 0.65 <i>F</i> = 1.591 <i>t</i> = 0.5184	24.90 ± 0.82	99.49 ± 0.91	99.82 ± 0.97	99.90 ± 0.43

Conclusions :

The proposed methods exploit the various functional groups in BUCZ molecule. The decreasing order of sensitivity (ϵ_{\max}) among the proposed methods is Method A > Method B > Method C respectively. The concomitants, which do not contain the functional groups chosen in the present investigation do not interfere in the color development by proposed methods. Thus the proposed methods are simple, sensitive and selective with reasonable precision and accuracy and constitute better alternatives to the reported ones in the assay of BUCZ in bulk form and pharmaceutical formulations (Table 3).

Structure of BUCZ

Buclizine [82-95-1] 1-[(4-chlorophenyl)

Phenylmethyl]-4-[(4-(1,1-dimethylethyl)phenyl)methyl]piperazine

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